

Rabies

Dr. Utkarsh Bansal*, Dr. Ekansh Rathoria**, Dr. Ajit Saxena#

*M.D. Pediatrics, Professor and Head, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India. **M.D. Pediatrics, Associate professor, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India #M.D. Pediatrics, Senior Consultant, Metro Hospital, Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

Rabies is a fatal tropical disease, claiming the lives of thousands of people annually in the endemic areas (mainly in Africa and Asia). It is a zoonotic viral disease where the viruses of the *Lyssavirus* genus are transmitted to the host via the saliva of an infected animal. Dogs are the most important reservoir for rabies viruses, and dog bites account for >99% of human cases. The infection involves the peripheral motor neurons initially, and florid symptoms are seen once the virus reaches the central nervous system. Development of the clinical disease invariably follows a fatal course. In case of an animal exposure, clinical diseases can be effectively prevented by a timely post-exposure prophylaxis, depending on the exposure category, which includes local wound decontamination, rabies vaccination, and immunoglobulin administration. The primary prevention is aimed at the vaccination of stray dogs. A holistic approach is required to eradicate human rabies, involving both the government and the public by spreading disease awareness, early post-exposure prophylaxis, adoption and immunization of stray dogs, and pre-exposure vaccination of at-risk people. Prevention is the key to achieve the WHO goal of reducing the number of cases of dog-mediated human rabies to zero by 2030.

INTRODUCTION

Rabies, a viral zoonotic disease caused by viruses of the *Lyssavirus* genus, was first described in the 4th century BC [1]. In the 1880's, Louis Pasteur discovered that a virus is a causative agent. The term rabies originated from the Latin word 'rabere' meaning 'to be mad'. Each year this deadly disease kills 59,000 people globally and causes about 3.7 million disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) to be lost [2]. One-third of the rabies deaths occur in India alone. Even though, around 17.4 million animal bites occur in India every year, only 5 million undergo post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) [3]. Dog-bite is responsible for more than 99% of the human cases [4]. Vaccination can prevent both animal and human rabies completely. Still, the disease remains enzootic (endemic in animals) in more than 150 countries of the world, and human rabies is the most common zoonotic disease. (Figure 1) The underprivileged population of Africa and Asia is the most affected, with children below the age of 15 years constituting around 40% of the cases [4]. Rabies is a disease of poverty, ignorance, and, misinformation. The principal strategy to interrupt the chain of transmission of rabies virus from dogs to other mammals is mass vaccination of dogs. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) 3.3 to end Neglected Tropical Diseases by 2030 and SDG 3.8 to achieve Universal Health Coverage have set a global goal of zero human rabies deaths by 2030 [5].

Figure 1. Distribution of dog-mediated rabies worldwide, based on 2016 data.

PATHOGEN

Rabies virus (RABV), is a bullet-shaped, negative-sense, unsegmented, single-stranded, enveloped RNA virus from the Mononegavirales order, the Rhabdoviridae family. (Figure 2) It is the prototype virus of the *Lyssavirus* genus and the most common causative agent of rabies and is transmitted by the bite of an infected mammal [6]. There are 14 species of *Lyssavirus* subdivided into 2 phylogroups [7]. RABV probably evolved from a bat-associated progenitor, and several host-switching events yielded a complex pattern of RABV variants.

The classic RABV belongs to phylogroup 1 (genotype 1), and is distributed worldwide naturally infecting a large variety of animals [8]. Seven *Lyssavirus* genotypes have been linked to human rabies, with genotype 1 being the most common. Several genetic variants are identified even within genotype 1. (Table 1) In general, an animal is a reservoir of a specific variant, but the cross-species transmission does occur. Bats are the chiropteran hosts who maintain most *Lyssavirus* species across the world apart from the wild carnivores [9,10]. RABV is maintained by dogs, foxes, wolves, jackals, bats, raccoons, skunks or mongoose, bats, and kudu (an herbivore). When a cross-species transmission (spill-over) occurs to other mammals, including humans, through neuroinvasion it results in rabies. Theoretically RABV can infect any mammal, but usually the spill-over infections are a 'dead-end' infection with no further transmission.

Table 1: The viral genome encodes 5 proteins [7]:

1. Nucleoprotein (N) bound-nucleic acids	Ribonucleoprotein complex, essential for viral replication and protein translation, comprises
2. RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (L)	
3. Phosphoprotein (P)	
4. Matrix (M)	Host-derived lipid envelope to form the structure leading to the host cell receptor binding.
5. Glycoproteins (G)	

The G protein is the most important among these and it includes the antigenic sites targeted by rabies vaccine-induced antibodies and rabies immunoglobulins (RIG) [11].

Figure 2: Structure of Rabies Virus

Exposure to infection

Animal-to-human exposures:

- Majority of rabies cases are caused from the bite of an infected dog, as the saliva is highly concentrated with RABV [12]. But bites from cats, cows, buffaloes, sheep, goats, pigs, donkeys, horses, camels, foxes, jackals, monkeys, mongoose, bears, and others can also transmit rabies. Dog rabies is characterized by changes to its normal behaviour, such as: unprovoked abnormal aggression, abnormal behaviour, restlessness, incoordination and paralysis, lethargy, hoarse barking and growling and hyper salivation. [13] The consequence of exposure depends on several factors: the wound severity, the location of the bite on the body, the quantity and variant (genotype) of virus, viral tissue tropism, and the timeliness of post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) [14]. If no treatment is given, the chances of developing rabies according to bites on different body location are: 30–60% (head, face, or neck), 15-40% (hand), and 0–10% (trunk and leg). [15] Viral load in the saliva of rabid animals may also vary during their disease [12]. The infection risk increases with deep bites reaching to the muscle, as the virus can then directly infect motor endplates. The bat RABV variants, in contrast to carnivore variants, can multiply in epidermal cells thus leading to clinical disease even by a scratch to the skin.

- Other routes of transmission: inhalation of aerosolized RABV in bat caves; handling and skinning of infected carcasses; and contamination of an open wound, scratch, abrasion, or mucous membrane by infected saliva or neural tissue [16,17,18].
- Dried saliva becomes non-infectious. Disinfectants that kill rabies virus are formalin, phenols, bleach, UV light (sunlight), and heat.
- Small mammals, such as mice, squirrels, and rabbits, are rarely reported to have rabies, and no animal-to-human transmission from these animals has been documented to date.

EPIDEMIOLOGY

Human-to-human RABV exposures:

- The saliva, tears, urine, and nervous tissues of human rabies cases contain RABV and a theoretical risk of transmission exists on exposure to these body fluids and tissues.
- RABV is not found in the blood or faeces.
- Human-to-human transmission of RABV is extremely rare, but caregivers are advised to use full barrier precautions.
- Transmission by breastfeeding is unlikely, although there is a paucity of evidence.
- Human-to-human transmission is only reported through RABV-infected patients' tissue and organ transplants, and a solitary case of RABV transmission in the perinatal period during pregnancy. [19,20].
- Aerosol inhalation while intubating a patient may pose a risk to the healthcare worker.

Other RABV exposures:

- Human rabies has not been reported following consumption of raw meat of a rabid animal.
- RABV has never been isolated from milk of rabid cows and consumption of raw milk has never been documented to cause human rabies.
- Inhalation of RABV-containing aerosols in laboratories handling highly concentrated live RABV can cause transmission [18,21]

INCUBATION PERIOD

The incubation period or eclipse phase can vary from weeks to years but usually it is 1–2 months depending on the exposure [22,23].

PATHOGENESIS

After inoculation, RABV replicates slowly in muscle or skin. This may account for the long incubation period [24]. It lies confined to the inoculated portion of the muscle, as a smouldering infection. The natural RABV does not activate the dendritic cells to activate the innate immune response. In conditions of a high inoculum deep in muscle, RABV can infect motor endplates directly, without undergoing replication in the muscle, which explains the shorter incubation period in such situations.

Centripetal propagation: From the motor endplates the highly neurotropic RABV enters peripheral nerves utilizing the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor at the neuromuscular junction (but not at sensory or autonomic endings) [25]. After entry, there is retrograde transport of RABV along axons via microtubules [26]. In the neuronal soma, the viral RNA via leads to the production of viral proteins by transcription. At the postsynaptic membranes, new virions are assembled and trans-synaptically transmitted to next-order neurons [27]. The virus finally reaches an area of the brain determined by the motor neurons innervating the place of entrance [27]. In the brain there is preferential localization in brain stem, thalamus, basal ganglia, spinal cord. This explains the autonomic dysfunction and relative cognition sparing.

Centrifugal propagation: Inside the brain, RABV disseminates, via centrifugal (anterograde) propagation that starts after replication in each infected neuron, and leads to viral transport to the ventral and dorsal roots and via the sensory nerves to the extraneural organs - ie, to muscle spindles, skin, salivary glands, heart, and blood vessels [29]. Referred pain and cross-organ sensitization have an anatomical underpinning in these pathways [30]. Organ dysfunction and dysautonomia in rabies patients could be explained by progressive functional changes in infected sensory innervation of extraneural organs (along with the heart and autonomic plexuses). Many rabies victims die as a result of uncontrolled cardiac dysrhythmia. The deficiency of tetrahydrobiopterin, an important cofactor for neuronal nitric oxide synthase, is thought to cause basilar artery spasm [31]. Vasospasm occurs after 5-8 days of hospitalization, around when coma supervenes in natural history.

CLINICAL FEATURES

Neuropathic pain at the bite site is the initial symptom of rabies which is caused by virus replication in the corresponding dorsal root ganglia and inflammation induced by a cellular immune response. Occasionally weakness of the bitten extremities can be the first presentation. Local neuropathic pain is more common in patients with bat RABV variant rabies

(70%) compared to dog-related cases (30%). The bat RABV variants show signs and symptoms of Horner's syndrome, and other atypical rabies features suggesting transmission via sensory or sympathetic skin innervation.

Rabies presents with two principal clinical forms, furious and paralytic [32]. In two-third of the cases an *encephalitic or "furious" rabies* develops beginning with prodromal symptoms, including fever, sore throat, malaise, headache, nausea and vomiting, and weakness. Paresthesia and pruritus develop at or near the site of the bite, gradually extending to the whole limb. Then the typical encephalitic symptoms appear including, agitation, depressed mentation, and, seizures. There can be alternating periods of lucidity and encephalopathy. Hydrophobia, and aerophobia, is considered *sine qua non* of human rabies. Even the sight of water or a drift of air on the face elicits phobic spasms of the pharynx, neck, and diaphragm muscles with agitation and fright, resulting in choking and aspiration. The illness has an unrelenting progression. Electrophysiologic or encephalographic activity dissociation is demonstrated with brainstem coma due to anterograde denervation.

One-third of the patients suffer from *paralytic or "dumb" rabies* which principally presents with fever and ascending motor weakness affecting both the limbs and the cranial nerves [33]. During the subacute disease progression, most patients also develop some form of encephalopathy [34]. Few patients of furious rabies may develop flaccid limb weakness during the stage of coma, which can be misidentified as paralytic rabies.

Non-classical features like objective sensory and motor deficits, choreiform movements of the bitten limb during prodromal phase, focal brain stem signs, myoclonus, hemiparesis, hemisensory loss, ataxia, vertigo, ocular myoclonus, hemichorea, repeated spontaneous ejaculation (autonomic dysfunction), paraparesis, facial & bulbar weakness can occur.

Death occurs due to neuronal dysfunction at the molecular level, with minimal or no signs of nonspecific or diffuse inflammation. Main cause of death is circulatory collapse. Survival after the clinical disease is exceptional with only 15 documented survivors, that too with severe sequelae in most [35]. The management is essentially to provide palliative care [23].

INVESTIGATIONS

Usually investigations are non-contributory and rabies is a clinical diagnosis based on history and exclusion of other possible diagnosis. There may be polymorphonuclear leucocytosis, and hyponatremia. Cerebro-Spinal fluid examination may be normal in 1/3 of patients in the first week of illness or show viral meningoencephalitis (increased lymphocytes & proteins). EEG and head CT may be normal early in illness. MRI may show abnormal, ill defined, increase signal intensity on T-2 images. The areas involved are brainstem, hippocampi, hypothalami, deep & subcortical white and grey matter. Gadolinium enhancement occurs only in late stages.[36] (Figure 3)

Figure 3: MRI (T2 images): bilateral hyperintensities in thalamus (a) and medulla (b)

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

- Severe cerebral infections,
- Tetanus,
- Intoxications and envenomation's.

- Autoimmune (anti-n-methyl d-aspartate receptor) encephalitis,
- Infectious encephalitis,
- Psychiatric illness,
- Drug abuse,
- Conversion disorders,
- Guillain-Barré syndrome (Paralytic rabies)

DIAGNOSIS

The WHO case definition for human rabies defines a human clinical case as follows: A subject presenting with an acute neurological syndrome (encephalitis) dominated by forms of hyperactivity (furious rabies) or paralytic signs (paralytic rabies) progressing towards coma and death, usually by cardiac or respiratory failure, typically within 7–10 days after the first sign [23]. Signs and symptoms of rabies include any of the following: hydrophobia, aerophobia, photophobia, paraesthesia or localized pain, dysphagia, localized weakness, nausea, or vomiting.

Though at the onset of disease, RABV is widely spread in the body, but Rabies-specific antibody is undetectable at that stage; so, have no diagnostic value [23]. Laboratory confirmation in humans can be obtained antemortem, and more reliably post-mortem, using saliva, spinal fluid, nuchal skin or tissue biopsies. The Negri body, a hallmark of rabies, is made up of clumped viral nucleocapsids that form cytoplasmic inclusions on routine histology. (Figure 4) Fluorescent antibody testing on brain tissue is the gold standard for diagnosis. The most sensitive assay for rabies diagnosis is a reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction.

Figure 4: Negri Bodies

The standard human case classification for rabies is:

- a.) *Suspected*: a case that is compatible with a clinical case definition
- b.) *Probable*: a suspected case plus a reliable history of contact with a suspected, probable, or confirmed rabid animal
- c.) *Confirmed*: a suspected or probable case that is laboratory-confirmed (usually post-mortem).

A case would also be considered confirmed even in the absence of clinical suspicion of encephalitis or a history of animal exposure if confirmed by appropriate laboratory diagnostic testing.

TREATMENT AND PROGNOSIS

Rabies is a fatal disease. Since 1990, 74 attempts at traditional critical care have resulted in only one survivor. Five of the sixteen patients survived without the need for critical care (including three patients with milder disease) and seven survived with the Milwaukee Protocol. The Milwaukee Protocol has a 20% success rate, but with poor neurologic outcome in one-third cases. [38] Precautions should be taken by the caregiver to avoid contamination of mucous membranes and wounds with saliva e.g. by washing hands, exercising good hygiene, and using personal protective equipment.

Treatment should focus on comfort, with heavy sedation barbiturates, morphine, intravenous fluids and avoidance of intubation or life-support measures, especially once the diagnosis is certain. The patient should be kept in a quiet room with subdued light and be protected from stimuli (e.g. loud noises, cold air) that are likely to increase spasms. There is no benefit of rabies immunoglobulin (RIG) or rabies vaccine once symptoms appear. The privacy, dignity and cultural needs of patients should be respected. Preserving the capacity of the family to communicate with their loved ones in their dying moments must be a priority. [39]

PREVENTION

Post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP)

PEP needs to be considered in the following conditions:

- Bites by all warm-blooded animals.
- Exposure to wild animals: treated as Category III exposure.
- Bites by Rodents: PEP is not recommended on exposure to domestic rats, hare, or rabbits. But in case of a rodent bites in forest areas PEP is recommended.
- Exposure to bats: Bat rabies has not been fully proved in India, hence PEP is not justified at this time. Consultation with infectious diseases expert is recommended.
- People who have been exposed closely to the secretions of a patient with rabies may be offered PEP as a precautionary measure.

Observation Period: The PEP should be started immediately after the exposure, without any delay. Only dogs and cats are subject to the ten-day observation period, while the natural history of rabies in other mammals not fully understood and therefore observation period is not applicable. The treatment may be modified if the suspected dog or cat involved in the incident is healthy after a 10-day observation period and PEP can be converted to pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) by skipping the vaccine dose on day 14 and administering it on day 28 while using IM regimen (Essen Schedule). While employing the ID route of administration, the entire course of vaccination should be given, regardless of the animal's status. [40]

Vaccination status of biting animals: Animals vaccinated against rabies do not suffer and transmit the disease. However, animal vaccine failures are common because of improper administration, inadequate doses, poor quality of the vaccine, or poor health status of the animal. Hence, irrespective of the vaccination status of the biting animal, the PEP should be given. [40]

Provoked versus unprovoked bite: It cannot be assumed that if a bite occurs due to provoking an animal, it is not rabid. Therefore, all bites should also be managed as exposure and PEP should be started immediately. [40]

Contraindications and Precautions: As rabies is a nearly 100% fatal disease, there is no contraindication to PEP.

- Pregnancy, lactation, infancy, old age, and concurrent illness are not the contraindications. The rabies vaccine has no adverse effects on a pregnant woman, the course of pregnancy, the fetus, or the breastfeeding mother.
- Individuals with HIV who are on antiretroviral therapy (ART) and are clinically and immunologically stable (normal CD4 percent >25% for children <5 years or CD4 cell count ≥ 200 cells/mm³ for children ≥ 5 years) can receive rabies immunization.
- For immunocompromised individuals (such as HIV-infected persons who are not receiving ART or who are receiving ART but do not meet minimum CD4 cell count criteria) with WHO category II and III RABV exposure: PEP according to category III exposure is recommended in all cases, even if previously immunized.
- Chloroquine used for malaria treatment or prophylaxis may reduce the response to the intradermal (ID) route so intramuscular (IM) route is preferred in such cases.

As in case of any immunization, the vaccinated persons should be kept under medical supervision for at least 15-20 minutes post-vaccination. Previous reaction to any component of a vaccine is a contraindication to the use of the same vaccine for PEP or PrEP. [40]

Duration after exposure: As rabies usually has a long and variable incubation period, the opportunity to initiate PEP and protect the individual should always be utilized. PEP is effective till RABV has reached the nervous system. Therefore, cases coming even months or years after a possible rabies exposure should be evaluated and treated as if the event had occurred recently. [40]

The indication and procedure for PEP depend on the type of contact with the suspected rabid animal and immunization status of the patient (Table 2) [22]:

Table 2: Category of exposure and recommended Post Exposure Prophylaxis	
Category of exposure to suspect rabid animal	Post-exposure measures
Category I – touching or feeding animals, licks on intact skin (i.e., no exposure)	Local treatment of the wound
Category II – nibbling of uncovered skin, minor scratches or abrasions without bleeding	Local treatment of the wound + Immediate vaccination
Category III – single or multiple transdermal bites or scratches, licks on broken skin; contamination of mucous membrane with saliva from licks, exposures to bats, wild animals, bites in forest areas	Local treatment of the wound + Immediate vaccination + administration of RIG

PEP consists of:

- a.) thorough washing and flushing of the wound,
- b.) a series of rabies vaccination promptly started after exposure,
- c.) RIG infiltration into and around the wound, promptly after exposure, if indicated.

LOCAL WOUND CARE

- The wound(s) should be washed immediately with soap and water for 10–15 minutes. In absence of soap, wound should be flushed with water. This is the most effective rabies first-aid treatment [41].
- The wound(s) should be meticulously cleaned with 70% ethanol/alcohol or povidone-iodine.
- Wound treatment should be done, even if the patient presents late, as RABV can remain and multiply for a long time at the bite site.
- The wound(s) should not be treated/touched with bare hands by healthcare workers.
- If the eyes and mucosa are exposed they should be thoroughly rinsed with water.
- The use of irritants (such as chiles, oil, turmeric, lime, salt, etc) is needless and harmful. If irritants have been applied to the wounds, they should be gently washed with soap to remove the external applicant/s, then flushed with plenty of water.

Suturing: Any suturing of the wound should be avoided is possible. If suturing is essential for hemostasis, then first RIG should be infiltrated in the wound. The suturing should be delayed for several hours to allow diffusion of the RIG through the tissues. Sutures should be loose and not interfere with free bleeding and drainage. Secondary suture of bite wounds results in better cosmetic outcomes. [39]

Tetanus and antibiotic prophylaxis: National guidelines should be followed while administering tetanus prophylaxis. A proper course of antibiotics may be recommended to prevent sepsis in the wound(s). Analgesics can be used. Covering the wound with dressings or bandages should be avoided. [39]

The majority of deaths from rabies occur because a timely and effective PEP is not administered [42]. Following an exposure, prompt PEP is 100 percent effective in preventing rabies [43] However, delay in seeking PEP, improper wound care, unnoticed wounds, direct nerve inoculation, and lack of patient compliance with vaccination schedules, contribute to PEP failure and subsequent death [43]. If the virus is directly inoculated into the nerve, it avoids the immune system and the effect of the rabies vaccines, and can be only neutralized by RIG.

RABIES VACCINES

In 1885 A.D., Louis Pasteur and Emile Roux produced the first live attenuated injectable rabies vaccine, based on inactivated homogenates of RABV-infected rabbit nerve tissue. It was followed by Semple vaccine, Fuenzalida vaccine, and Duck embryo vaccine in the coming years. Modern cell-culture vaccines came into picture in 1970. [44] Since 1984, WHO has strongly recommended discontinuation of production and use of nerve tissue vaccines and their replacement by modern, concentrated, purified cell culture rabies vaccines (CCVs) [23]. Nerve tissue vaccines are more reactogenic and are less immunogenic than CCVs. Rabies CCVs are extremely efficient, as well as safe, and tolerable.

WHO recommends the use of CCVs with a potency of at least 2.5 IU per vial (0.5 mL or 1.0 mL vaccine by volume after reconstitution, depending on the type of vaccine) [45,46].

The currently available vaccines are: [47]

- Cell culture vaccines (CCVs)
 - purified chick embryo cell vaccine (PCECV),
 - human diploid cell vaccine (HDCV),
 - purified Vero cell rabies vaccine (PVRV)
- Purified Duck Embryo vaccine (PDEV).

Indications:

- Regardless of age or bodyweight, all animal bite victims of Category II and III exposures require the same number of injections and dose per injection for PEP.
- PrEP in the high-risk population

Storage: Marketed in freeze-dried (lyophilized) form, and recommended to be kept and transported at a temperature range of 2-8°C and protected from sunlight in which they are stable for 3 years. [40]

Efficacy and effectiveness: All CCVs have almost equal efficacy and any one can be used. They induce protective antibodies in more than 99% of vaccines following PrEP/PEP. Studies from many countries in South-East Asia have established the effectiveness of CCVs for both PrEP and PEP. [48].

Duration of immunity: The CCVs produce immunological memory, and individuals who had received their primary series 5–21 years previously with no detectable antibody levels showed a good anamnestic responses after booster vaccination [49].

Adverse Events Following Immunization (AEFI): The CCVs are the least reactogenic rabies vaccines available today. Mild systemic AEFI include headache, malaise, nausea, gastrointestinal side effects, and fever. Symptomatic treatment may be needed. Erythema that may be minor or transient, pain and swelling may occur at the site of injection, especially in the ID route [49]. Serious AEFI, of allergic or neurological nature, occur rarely.

Switch from one vaccine brand/type to the other: In routine practice, switching from one brand/type of CCV to another should be discouraged. However, if there are no other options, the available brand/type may be used to complete PEP [48].

Dose and route: For both PEP and PrEP, vaccines can be administered by either the ID or IM route. The dose is 1 mL IM for HDCV, PCEV, PDEV, and 0.5 mL for PVRV at all ages. One ID dose is 0.1 mL of vaccine. The ID schedules are beneficial in terms of cost, dose, and time savings [50].

The deltoid region, as well as the anterolateral thigh or suprascapular regions, are used for ID injections in people of all ages. The deltoid area of the arm is the recommended site for IM administration for adults and children ≥ 2 years of age, and the anterolateral area of the thigh is recommended IM site for children < 2 years. [40]

Rabies vaccine should not be administered IM in the gluteal area, because of low absorption due to the presence of adipose tissue. If 2 or more doses of rabies vaccine are administered at the same visit, they should be injected in different sites/limbs. Opened vials should be used within 6–8 hours [51,52]. If any doses are delayed, vaccination should be resumed, not restarted. ID route has poor efficacy in immune-compromised individuals or individuals receiving chloroquine, hydroxychloroquine, or long-term corticosteroid or other immunosuppressive therapy, so IM route is preferred in such cases. [40]

Seroconversion following vaccination: Humoral immunity provides protection against rabies. Anti-rabies neutralizing antibody titre of ≥ 0.5 IU/ml is considered as adequate seroconversion post-vaccination. This level is achieved in most healthy individuals by day 14 of a PEP regimen, with or without simultaneous administration of rabies immunoglobulin. [40]

Schedule of PEP Vaccination:

- **IM schedule:** The standard schedule is Essen protocol [53]. One-site IM (1 vial) on days 0, 3, 7, 14, and 28. After exposure, the first dose should be given as soon as possible. Day 0 of the PEP series is assigned to this date. Following it further doses should be given on days 3, 7, 14, and 28.

Figure 1: Essen Schedule (5-dose)

- **ID schedule:** This involves Updated Thai Red Cross Regimen. Two-site ID (0.1 ml) on days 0, 3, 7, and 28. (one on each deltoid area, an inch above the insertion of deltoid muscle) [54]. Day 0 is the date of administration of the first dose of rabies vaccine.

Figure 2: Updated Thai Red Cross Schedule

Intradermal administration is not recommended in individual practice. The criteria for the selection of anti-rabies centre for ID use are:

- Attendance of a minimum of 50 patients per day for PEP
- Has adequately trained staff to give ID inoculation
- Can maintain the cold chain and ensure supply of disposable syringes and needles.

Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis (PrEP)

High risk groups for PrEP [49,55]:

- *Continuous exposure:* Lab employees working on rabies research and biologics manufacture.
- *Frequent exposure:* Veterinarians, laboratory professionals involved in rabies diagnosis, medical and paramedical staff treating rabies patients, dog catchers, zookeepers, and forest staff.
- *Infrequent exposure:*
 - Postmen, policemen, and courier boys
 - Travelers to rabies endemic countries who intend to backpack/trek.
- The Indian Association of Pediatrics (IAP) has recommended PrEP for all children. This may be considered voluntarily.

Schedule of PrEP Vaccination [56]:

IM schedule: One-site IM (1 vial) on days 0, 7 and booster on either day 21 or 28.

ID schedule: Two-site ID (0.1 ml) on days 0, 7, and booster on either day 21 or 28.

Figure 3: Pre-exposure prophylaxis

High-risk groups should have their viral neutralizing antibody (VNA) titres checked every 6 months during the initial two years following their primary vaccination. A booster dose should be administered if it is < 0.5 IU/ml [57]. Subsequently, sera- monitoring is recommended every two years. When serologic testing is not available, a 5-year booster immunization is an acceptable option. Boosters whenever indicated are given as one-site ID or one-site IM vaccine administration. [39]

Re-exposure in previously vaccinated persons: In patients who have a documented previous full PrEP or PEP, on re-exposure [40]:

- Proper wound management should be done in all cases.
- Just proper wound washing would be required if the animal bite victim has documented proof of complete PEP or PrEP within the previous three months.
- RIG administration is not needed.
- One-site ID (0.1 ml) on days 0 and 3
- One-site IM (1 vial) on days 0 and 3 [58].

Figure 4: Post-exposure prophylaxis in previously vaccinated

People who have previously received full post-exposure treatment with neural tissue vaccines (NTV) or vaccine of unproven potency or CANNOT document complete previous PEP or PrEP treatment should be treated as fresh case and given full PEP.

Co-administration: Evidence supports safe co-administration of CCVs with other inactivated and with live vaccines [55, 59]

The Latest WHO (2018) recommended schedule [4]:

Schedule of PEP Vaccination:

- IM schedule: One-site IM (1 vial) on days 0, 3, 7, and any day between 14 to 28 days.
Two-sites IM (2 vials) on days 0 and 1-site IM (1 vial) on days 7, 21
- ID schedule: Two-site ID (0.1 ml) on days 0, 3 and 7

Schedule of PrEP Vaccination:

- IM schedule: One-site IM (1 vial) on days 0 and 7
- ID schedule: Two-site ID (0.1 ml) on days 0 and 7

Schedule of Re-exposure of previously immunized:

- IM schedule: One-site IM (1 vial) on days 0 and 3
- ID schedule: One-site ID (0.1 ml) on days 0 and 3
Four-sites ID (0.1 ml) on day 0

But this schedule has yet not been approved by DGCI, so not recommended till approval.

PASSIVE IMMUNIZATION**RABIES IMMUNOGLOBULINS (RIG)**

After exposure to rabies, RIG provides passive immunization by neutralizing RABV at the wound site before the immune system can respond to the vaccine by producing Viral Neutralizing Antibodies (VNAs).

Indications [40]:

- All category III animal bite exposures cases
- All wild animal exposures (classified as category III exposures)
- Category II and III exposure in immunocompromised persons such as HIV/AIDS patients, patients on immunosuppressive medication (steroids/cancer chemotherapy), congenital agammaglobulinemia, etc.

Types of RIGs [40]:

- **Equine Rabies Immunoglobulin (ERIG):** ERIG is produced by hyper-immunization of horses and heterologous origin. The newer ERIGs have highly purified Fab 2' fragments and thus significantly reduced adverse events. Being a heterologous product, it carries a risk of an anaphylactic reaction (1/150,000). A skin test before administering ERIG is not needed because testing does not accurately predict adverse reactions, and ERIG should be given irrespective of the result of the test. The treating physician should be prepared to manage anaphylaxis.
- **Human Rabies Immunoglobulin (HRIG):** HRIG is of homologous origin and is relatively free from the side effects. Because of the longer half-life, HRIG is given at half the dose of ERIG.

Dosages of RIG:

- ERIG: 40 IU per kg body weight
- HRIG: 20 IU per kg body weight

Administration of RIG [39,40]:

- Before administering the RIG, it should be brought to room temperature (25°C to 30°C).
- RIG delivers VNAs at the site of exposure before the patient's antibodies are produced as a result of vaccination.
- Only a single dose of RIG is given, preferably at or shortly after the start of PEP.
- RIG is not recommended beyond the seventh day after receiving the first dose of the rabies vaccine, regardless of whether the doses were given on days 3 and 7. As by this time circulating VNAs are formed.
- The complete dose, or as much as anatomically possible should be infiltrated (while avoiding probable compartment syndrome), into or as close to the wound(s) or exposure sites as possible.
- For large or multiple wounds, RIG can be diluted with physiologically buffered saline if necessary to ensure complete infiltration of all wounds.
- If there is a high possibility of further tiny wounds (e.g., if a kid does not report all wounds), inject the remaining RIG volume IM as close to the predicted exposure site as possible, to the anatomically practicable extent.
- RIG should not be injecting into blood vessels
- In case of mucosal exposure without a wound rinsing with RIG is advised, along with an IM injection of the remaining RIG
- An IM injection of RIG is indicated in the case of probable RABV exposure via aerosols.
- Rabies vaccine should be given on a different anatomical location from the site of RIG administration.

A systematic review concluded that maximum infiltration of the RIG dose (calculated by body weight) into and around the wound is effective and the IM administration of the additional remaining dose had very limited benefits [60,61,62]. The remaining RIG can be used for other patients, especially if RIG is in short supply [63,64]. Data from rabies-endemic

settings have shown that even in the absence of RIG, proper wound management with early and complete PEP course, >99% of patients do not develop rabies.

It is estimated that globally, less than 2% of category III exposed patients receive RIG, due to short supply and high cost [65, 66]. If the amount of available RIG is limited, its allocation should be prioritized [67]. The cases with the highest priority to receive RIG are:

- category III exposed patients with multiple bites;
- those with deep wounds,
- bites to those parts of the body which are highly innervated, such as the head, neck, genitalia, and hands;
- patients with severe immunodeficiency;
- cases in which the biting animal has been diagnosed with rabies, whether it is proven or suspected;
- where a bat has bitten, scratched or exposed a mucosal membrane

RABIES MONOCLONAL ANTIBODIES (RmAbs)

The 2018 WHO position paper on rabies stresses on the judicious use of RIG given the supply limitations, and now include rabies mAbs in its recommendations stating that mAb products, rather than RIG, should be used if they are available [68]. Monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) are clones derived from a single parent cell. They have a high affinity for their epitope, the specific site of the antigen/protein they bind to. There are four types of mAbs (Figure 5):

1. **Murine:** entirely derived from a murine source and are the first generation, developed in 1986. Their use can lead to allergic reactions in humans. As they may be immunogenic, antibodies can be generated against them which may reduce their efficacy or cause reactions. In other words, they are similar to ERIG.
2. **Chimeric:** was developed by increasing the human component in the antibody. Here, the variable regions are of murine origins whereas the constant regions are of humans. These can also cause an allergy but with a lower risk and are immunogenic.
3. **Humanized:** except for the component of the antibody that binds to its target, it is mostly produced from a human source. Reaction risk is lower.
4. **Human:** entire antibody is derived from a human source and is the safest mAb with the least chance of reactions.

Figure 5: Types of Monoclonal Antibodies

At the 1990 consultation, experts agreed that “cocktails” containing more than one mAb should be pursued to reduce the risk of failure due to escape mutants; cocktails should contain only IgG isotype mAbs with high affinity and broad specificity; should be tested against a variety of circulating viruses; and should be adjusted to regional needs dependent on local circulating viruses [69]. MAb against the RABV that neutralize RABV and other lyssaviruses are specific to one of five distinct antigenic sites on the RABV G protein (antigenic sites I, II, III, IV, and minor site a) with the vast majority of them recognizing either antigenic site II or III. Antigenic site II is discontinuous and conformation-dependent, whereas antigenic site III is predicted to be continuous and conformation-dependent. (Figure 6)

Figure 6: Rabies virus Glycoprotein (G Protein)

Rabishield:

- Serum Institute of India Pvt. Ltd. (SIPL) manufactured the Rabishield which was tested in a phase 2/3 clinical trial and was licensed in India in 2016 and launched in 2017 [70,71].
- Rabishield is a single human IgG1 type mAb that binds to ectodomain of G glycoprotein. HuMAb 17C7 recognizes a conformational epitope on the RABV G protein, which includes antigenic site III.
- The mAb was originally derived from a transgenic mouse and developed by Mass Biologics (Boston, MA, USA) under the name 17C7 before being transferred to SIPL.
- Dose: 3.33 IU per kg body weight [71,72].
- One potential source of concern regarding this product is that it contains only one mAb, which was shown to be incapable of neutralizing a rare rabies variant identified in a Peruvian bat. [71,73,74,75]. The SAGE working group on rabies discussed this issue and decided that it targets a highly conserved epitope of the rabies G protein and had been proved to be widely neutralizing with just a minor risk in the Americas region [76].

TwinRab

- Produced by Zydus Cadila in India. The product is made up of two murine monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) that bind to distinct locations on the rabies G protein.
- The mAbs for rabies miromavimab (M777-16-3 from the Animal Diseases Research Institute, Canada) and docaravimab (62-71-3 from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, USA) were donated by WHO Collaborating Centres to Zydus Cadila.
- In phase 3, randomized study, comparing anti-rabies mAb cocktail (Twinrab) in contrast to HRIG, the GMTs of the antibodies induced with Twinrab were found to be non-inferior to those induced with HRIG, with no statistically significant difference between the two groups and a similar adverse effect profile [77].
- Docaravimab (IgG2b isotype) specifically binds to the sites I or III and Miromavimab (IgG1 isotype) specifically binds to the site II on G protein of rabies virus envelope.
- Both rabies and rabies-like virus strains isolated from canine, human, and bovine sources are bound and neutralized by two mAbs individually, thereby blocking their entrance into surrounding cells. [78].
- One issue with murine cocktail mAbs is the development of auto-antibodies. In the phase 1 trial, 2 people out of 18 developed ADA (11%). In the Phase 2 trial, 4 individuals developed ADA against M777-16-3, and 5 developed against 62-71-3 during days 14 to 42 – in total about 9 of 12 developed ADA (75%). The generation of auto-antibodies (ADAs) may affect the potency of the monoclonals.
- Dose is 40 IU per kg of body weight [79].

Indian Academy of Pediatrics (IAP) Advisory Committee on Vaccines and Immunization Practices (ACVIP) highly recommended the use mAbs for rabies PEP [80].

THE WAY AHEAD

Cost-effectiveness of Universal PrEP

Cost-effectiveness of programmatic PrEP, including potential benefits and relative costs of inclusion of rabies PrEP in routine childhood immunization programs, were modelled for rabies-endemic settings. Results suggest that PrEP as a large-scale public health intervention would be substantially more expensive than PEP provision combined with mass dog vaccination campaigns. In Chad, the cost invested per DALY averted over 20 years has been estimated to be US\$ 3270 for routine PrEP with PEP, compared to US\$ 43 for a PEP-only strategy, and US\$ 54 for a PEP plus mass dog vaccination strategy [81]. Results indicate that PrEP for entire populations might become cost-neutral only in settings with an

extremely high incidence of dog bites (>5000 per 100000 persons per year) and high RIG use in unvaccinated individuals, resulting in a higher direct cost of PEP. [82].

IAP ACVIP recommends universal PrEP for children to reduce the number of human rabies cases and the program can be made cost effective by using the ID regime. [47]

SURVEILLANCE AND MONITORING

Accurate data are required for setting regional, national, and local priorities for control programs, surveillance, and research. Rabies is frequently underreported in official reports, leading to a vicious circle of ignorance and neglect. Surveillance should include human and animal rabies cases, animal bites, with stratification by the age group of bite victims, categories of exposure and biting animal species, and investigation of biting animals, as well as PEP usage and patient compliance with PEP regimens. Pharmacovigilance and reporting of adverse events in individuals who received PEP or PrEP should be conducted. [4]

Table 1: Key points for Office Practice:

- Rabies is a universally fatal disease with no cure, prevention is the only key.
- High index of suspicion for rabies should be kept in cases with animal exposure and atypical symptoms.
- Exposure or bites by all mammals, except domestic rodents, require PEP.
- Consumption of raw meat or raw milk of a rabid animal does not require PEP.
- All exposures by wild animals are considered Category III exposure.
- In case of any doubt about the exposure, PEP should be offered.
- In Immunocompromised patients, Category II exposure is also treated as Category III exposure.
- Irrespective of the vaccination status of the biting animal, PEP should be given.
- PEP should be started immediately after the exposure (Not after the observation period of 10 days)
- Wound cleaning is a must in all categories of bites, with soap and water for 15 minutes, followed by application of 70% ethanol/alcohol or povidone-iodine.
- Healthcare workers should not touch/treat the wound with bare hands.
- Bandaging and suturing of the wound should be avoided, if unavoidable should be done only after RIG/RmAb infiltration.
- Pregnancy, lactation, infancy, old age, and concurrent illness are not a contraindication to PEP (including RIG/RmAb).
- PEP: Category II (Vaccine) & Category III (Vaccine + RIG/RmAb).
- PEP: One-site IM (1 vial) on days 0, 3, 7, 14, and 28.
- PrEP: One-site IM (1 vial) on days 0, 7, and either day 21 or 28.
- Rabies vaccines are given in the same dose and schedule at all ages, sex and body weight.
- Rabies vaccine should never be given in the gluteal region.
- Long & variable incubation period provides an opportunity to initiate PEP even years later including RIG.
- RIG/RmAb is indicated with even a micro-droplet of blood visible at bite wound.
- RmAb preferable to HRIG or ERIG (safer, effective & economical).
- Dose of ERIG: 40 IU/kg, HRIG: 20 IU/kg, Rabishield: 3.33 IU/kg, Twinrab: 40 IU/kg.
- RIG/RmAb should be infiltrated into or as close to the wound.
- RIG/RmAb should not be given beyond the 7th day after receiving the first dose of the rabies vaccine.
- Rabies vaccine should be given on a different anatomical location from the site of administration of RIG/RmAb.
- In mucosal exposure without a wound rinsing with RIG is advised, along with an IM injection of the remaining RIG/RmAb.
- An IM injection of RIG/RmAb is indicated in the case of probable RABV exposure via aerosols.
- On re-exposure (after a complete PEP or PrEP): within 3 months: only proper wound washing; beyond 3 months: One-site IM (1 vial) on days 0 and 3, RIG is not needed; and in immunocompromised patients: full PEP including RIG/RmAb if indicated is given.
- Always document the exposure category on the patient record sheet and mention the appropriate PEP.
- Informed consent should be taken from patients refusing PEP.
- Counsel parents to take PrEP for children, as they are at a higher risk, due to their short stature (bites close to brain) and exploratory nature (provocation of animals).
- Counsel parents to vaccinate their pets, educate their children to report any exposure immediately, and avoid contact with unfamiliar animals.
- Counsel patients that following proper, timely, and complete PEP is 100% preventive from rabies.

PREVENTION

Prevention of rabies relies heavily on the awareness of at-risk populations about the disease. Efforts to promote awareness should include education, engagement with relevant sectors on animal bite prevention, responsible dog ownership, and prompt first aid after exposure [83]. These preventive measures may also impact other diseases and bite injuries (e.g., echinococcosis, leishmaniasis, leptospirosis, etc). Mass dog vaccination aiming at 70% cover-age in endemic areas interrupts RABV transmission at its animal source and saves human lives [84,85]. WHO and its partners [86] have endorsed a target of Zero Human Rabies Deaths from dog-transmitted rabies by 2030 (Zero by 30) [87]. This is aligned with Goal 3 of the Sustainable Development Goals, to end epidemics of communicable diseases including neglected tropical diseases by 2030 [88].

ORAL ANIMAL RABIES VACCINE

A new strategy in the fight against rabies deaths: The WHO and World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE) support the effective and safe use of oral rabies vaccines for dogs [89]. Getting the dogs to consume rabies vaccine bait is far faster, easier, and more practical than capturing them in nets and administering rabies vaccinations. It also cost-effective by allowing more dogs to be vaccinated daily.

Vaccines with better thermostability, a longer shelf-life, and smaller packaging volume would make delivery easy. Vaccines with improved profiles covering different *lyssaviruses* are needed. More research is needed to demonstrate the potential benefits, feasibility, and cost-effectiveness of new vaccine delivery techniques such as needle-free jet injection, microneedle injection systems, and topical patches. Studies on immunization of individuals with repeat exposures are encouraged, to understand the optimal spacing of PEP and the number of series needed over a lifetime. It would be helpful to learn more about the factors that influence seroconversion and clinical outcomes in immunocompromised persons. Studies on single-visit PrEP in rabies-endemic areas, will be helpful. To enhance the efficacy and coverage of RABV. neutralization products containing two or more mAbs with non-overlapping epitopes need to be developed. [4]

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR:

Dr. Utkarsh Bansal

M.D. Pediatrics, Professor and Head, Department of Pediatrics,
Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India.
email : utkarsh1003@gmail.com

FINANCIAL SUPPORT & SPONSORSHIP

NIL

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DISCLOSURE

There is no conflict of interest to be declared by the authors

REFERENCES:

1. **Fooks AR, Cliquet F, Finke S, Freuling C, Hemachudha T, Mani RS, et al.** Rabies. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*. 2017 Nov 30;3:17091. doi: 10.1038/nrdp.2017.91.
2. **Hampson K, Coudeville L, Lembo T, Sambo M, Kieffer A, Attlan M, et al.** Estimating the global burden of endemic canine rabies. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*. 2015 Apr 16;9(4):e0003709.
3. **Sudarshan MK.** Assessing burden of rabies in India: WHO sponsored national multicentric rabies survey, 2003. *Indian Journal of Community Medicine*. 2005 Jul 1;30(3):100.
4. **WHO position paper.** Rabies vaccines. *Wkly Epidemiol Record*. 2018;93:201-220.
5. **Addisu A, Adriaensen W, Balew A, Asfaw M, Diro E, Djirmay AG, et al.** Neglected tropical diseases and the sustainable development goals: an urgent call for action from the front line. *BMJ global health*. 2019 Feb 1;4(1):e001334.
6. **Badrane H, Tordo N.** Host switching in Lyssavirus history from the Chiroptera to the Carnivora orders. *Journal of virology*. 2001 Sep 1;75(17):8096-104.
7. **Fooks AR, Banyard AC, Horton DL, Johnson N, McElhinney LM, Jackson AC.** Current status of rabies and prospects for elimination. *The Lancet*. 2014 Oct 11;384(9951):1389-99.
8. **Walker PJ, Blasdel KR, Calisher CH, Dietzgen RG, Kondo H, Kurath G, et al.** ICTV Report Consortium. ICTV Virus Taxonomy Profile: Rhabdoviridae. *J Gen Virol*. 2018 Apr;99(4):447-448. doi: 10.1099/jgv.0.001020.
9. **Birhane MG, Cleaton JM, Monroe BP, Wadhwa A, Orciari LA, Yager P, et al.** Rabies surveillance in the United States during 2015. *Journal of the American Veterinary Medical Association*. 2017 May 15;250(10):1117-30.
10. **Rupprecht CE et al.** In: *Plotkin SA, Orenstein WA, Offit PA, editors. Vaccines*. 7th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier Saunders. 2017:918-942.
11. **World Health Organization, Geneva, 2017.** The immunological basis for immunization series: module 17: rabies vaccines. Available from: https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/259511/9789241513371_eng.pdf;sequence=1. Accessed on 20 April 2021.
12. **Hemachudha T, Ugolini G, Wacharapluesadee S, Sungkarat W, Shuangshoti S, Laothamatas J.** Human rabies: neuropathogenesis, diagnosis, and management. *The Lancet Neurology*. 2013 May 1;12(5):498-513.
13. **WHO.** Frequently asked questions about rabies for the General Public. 2018. Available from: https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/ntds/rabies/rabies-general-public-faqs.pdf?sfvrsn=ac59055f_4. Accessed on 30 April 2021.
14. **Shim E, Hampson K, Cleaveland S, Galvani AP.** Evaluating the cost-effectiveness of rabies post-exposure prophylaxis: a case study in Tanzania. *Vaccine*. 2009 Nov 27;27(51):7167-72.
15. **Cleaveland S, Fevre EM, Kaare M, Coleman PG.** Estimating human rabies mortality in the United Republic of Tanzania from dog bite injuries. *Bulletin of the world Health Organization*. 2002;80:304-10.
16. **Dutta JK, Dutta TK, Das AK.** Human rabies: modes of transmission. *The Journal of the Association of Physicians of India*. 1992 May 1;40(5):322-4.
17. **Constantine DG.** Rabies transmission by air in bat caves. Atlanta, Ga. EUA United State Department of Health, Education, and Welfare. *Pub. Health Serv. Public*. 1967;1617.
18. **Winkler WG, Fashinell TR, Leffingwell L, Howard P, Conomy JP.** Airborne rabies transmission in a laboratory worker. *Jama*. 1973 Dec 3;226(10):1219-21.
19. **Rupprecht CE, Nagarajan T, Ertl H.** Current status and development of vaccines and other biologics for human rabies prevention. *Expert Review of Vaccines*. 2016 Jun 2;15(6):731-49.
20. **Aguèmon CT, Tarantola A, Zoumènou E, Goyet S, Assouto P, Ly S, et al.** Rabies transmission risks during peripartum—Two cases and a review of the literature. *Vaccine*. 2016 Apr 4;34(15):1752-7.
21. **Johnson N, Phillipotts R, Fooks AR.** Airborne transmission of lyssaviruses. *Journal of medical microbiology*. 2006 Jun 1;55(6):785-90.
22. **WHO.** Fact sheet on rabies. 2021. Available from <https://www.who.int/en/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/rabies>, Accessed on 21 June 2021.
23. **WHO.** Expert Consultation on Rabies, third report: WHO Technical Series Report No.1012, Geneva, 2018 (ISBN 978-92-4-121021-8). 2018. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-TRS-1012>, Accessed on 22 May 2021.
24. **Charlton KM, Nadin-Davis S, Casey GA, Wandeler AI.** The long incubation period in rabies: delayed progression of infection in muscle at the site of exposure. *Acta neuropathologica*. 1997 Jun 1;94(1):73-7.
25. **Ugolini G.** Rabies virus as a transneuronal tracer of neuronal connections. *Advances in virus research*. 2011 Jan 1;79:165-202.
26. **Ugolini G.** Advances in viral transneuronal tracing. *Journal of neuroscience methods*. 2010 Dec 15;194(1):2-0.
27. **Klingen Y, Conzelmann KK, Finke S.** Double-labeled rabies virus: live tracking of enveloped virus transport. *Journal of virology*. 2008 Jan 1;82(1):237-45.

28. **Schnell MJ, McGettigan JP, Wirblich C, Papaneri A.** The cell biology of rabies virus: using stealth to reach the brain. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*. 2010 Jan;8(1):51-61.
29. **Jackson AC, Ye H, Phelan CC, Ridaura-Sanz C, Zheng Q, Li Z, et al.** Extraneural organ involvement in human rabies. *Laboratory investigation; a journal of technical methods and pathology*. 1999 Aug 1;79(8):945-51.
30. **Christianson JA, Davis BM.** The role of visceral afferents in disease. *Translational pain research: from mouse to man*. 2010:51-76.
31. **Willoughby RE, Roy-Burman A, Martin KW, Christensen JC, Westenkirschner DF, Fleck JD, et al.** Generalised cranial artery spasm in human rabies. *Developments in biologicals*. 2008 Jan 1;131:367-75.
32. **Hemachudha T, Laothamatas J, Rupprecht CE.** Human rabies: a disease of complex neuropathogenetic mechanisms and diagnostic challenges. *The Lancet Neurology*. 2002 Jun 1;1(2):101-9.
33. **Hemachudha T, Wacharapluesadee S, Mitrabhakdi E, Wilde H, Morimoto K, Lewis RA.** Pathophysiology of human paralytic rabies. *Journal of neurovirology*. 2005 Jan;11(1):93-100.
34. **Gadre G, Satishchandra P, Mahadevan A, Suja MS, Madhusudana SN, Sundaram C, et al.** Rabies viral encephalitis: clinical determinants in diagnosis with special reference to paralytic form. *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery & Psychiatry*. 2010 Jul 1;81(7):812-20.
35. **Jackson AC.** Human Rabies: a 2016 Update. *Curr Infect Dis Rep*. 2017;18(11).
36. **Hammond GW.** *Principles and Practice of Pediatric Infectious Diseases*. 5th Ed. Philadelphia. Elsevier.2018. Rabies virus. p 1176–1181
37. **Rhodney E, Wiloughby Jr.** *Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics*. 21st Ed. Philadelphia. Elsevier.2020. Chapter 300, Rabies. p 1174-1176
38. **Milwaukee Protocol**, version 6 (updated November 2018). Available from: https://www.mcw.edu/-/media/MCW/Departments/Pediatrics/Infectious-Diseases/Milwaukee_protocol.pdf?la=en. Accessed on 30 April 2021.
39. **WHO.** Frequently asked questions about rabies for Clinicians. 2018. Available from: https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/ntds/rabies/rabies-clinicians-faqs-20sep2018.pdf?sfvrsn=97d94712_4. Accessed on 30 April 2021.
40. **National Centre for Disease Control.** *National Guidelines for Rabies Prophylaxis*, 2019. Available from: <https://ncdc.gov.in/WriteReadData/linkimages/NationalGuidelinesforRabiesprophylaxis2019.pdf>. Accessed on 30 April 2021.
41. **Kaplan MM, Cohen D, Koprowski H, Dean D, Ferrigan L.** Studies on the local treatment of wounds for the prevention of rabies. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 1962;26(6):765.
42. **Hampson K et al.** Estimating the Global Burden of Endemic Canine Rabies. *Trop Dis*. 2015; 9 (5):e0003786.
43. **Wilde H.** Failures of post-exposure rabies prophylaxis. *Vaccine*. 2007 Nov 1;25(44):7605-9.
44. **Rupprecht CE, Nagarajan T, Ertl H.** *Plotkin's Vaccines*. 7th Ed. Philadelphia. Elsevier.2018. Chapter 50, Rabies Vaccine. p 1336-1372
45. **WHO** recommendations for inactivated rabies vaccine for human use produced in cell substrates and embryonated eggs, Annex 2. WHO Technical report series 941, Geneva, 2007. Available from <http://who.int/biologicals/publications/trs/areas/vaccines/rabies/Annex%20%20inactivated%20rabies%20vaccine.pdf?ua=1>, Accessed 24 May 2021.
46. **WHO** International Standard: Sixth International Standard for Rabies vaccine, NIBSC code: 07/162. 2013. Available from <http://www.nibsc.org/documents/ifu/07-162.pdf>, Accessed 25 May 2021.
47. **IAP** Advisory Committee on Vaccines and Immunization Practices, Indian Academy of Pediatrics. *Guidebook on Immunization 2018–2019*. 3rd Ed. New Delhi. Jaypee. 2020. Chapter 3.16, Rabies Vaccines. p 367-381
48. **Ravish HS, Sudarshan MK, Madhusudana SN, Annadani RR, Narayana DH, Belludi AY, et al.** Assessing safety and immunogenicity of post-exposure prophylaxis following interchangeability of rabies vaccines in humans. *Human vaccines & immunotherapeutics*. 2014 May 8;10(5):1354-8.
49. **WHO position paper.** Rabies vaccines. *Wkly Epidemiol Record*.2010;85:309-20.
50. **Hampson K, Abela-Ridder B, Bharti O, Knopf L, Léchenne M, Mindekem R, et al.** Modelling to inform prophylaxis regimens to prevent human rabies. *Vaccine*. 2019 Oct 3;37:A166-73.
51. **WHO.** Guidance Note: Vaccine Diluents (2015 revision). Available from http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/192741/1/WHO_IVB_15.08_eng.pdf, Accessed on 26 May 2021.
52. **WHO.** WHO policy statement: Multi-dose vial policy (MDVP)-Revision 2014. 2014; Available from: https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/135972/WHO_IVB_14.07_eng.pdf?sequence=1. Accessed on 26 May 2021.
53. **Shi N, Zhang Y, Zheng H, Zhu Z, Wang D, Li S, et al.** Immunogenicity, safety and antibody persistence of a purified vero cell cultured rabies vaccine (Speeda) administered by the Zagreb regimen or Essen regimen in post-exposure subjects. *Human vaccines & immunotherapeutics*. 2017 Jun 3;13(6):1338-45.

54. **Kundu BK, Meshram GG, Bhargava S, Meena O.** Cost savings of using updated Thai Red Cross intradermal regimen in a high-throughput anti-rabies clinic in New Delhi, India. *Tropical medicine and infectious disease*. 2019 Mar;4(1):50.
55. **Kessels JA, Recuenco S, Navarro-Vela AM, Deray R, Vigilato M, Ertl H,** et al. Pre-exposure rabies prophylaxis: a systematic review. *Bulletin of the world Health Organization*. 2017 Mar 1;95(3):210.
56. **WHO.** Evidence to recommendation Table 4: time and dose sparing PrEP. 2018. Available from http://www.who.int/immunization/policy/position_papers/rabies_time_dose_sparing_prep.pdf, Accessed on 27 May 2021.
57. **Parize P, Sommé J, Schaeffer L, Ribadeau-Dumas F, Benabdelkader S, Durand A,** et al. Systematic Booster after Rabies Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis to Alleviate Rabies Antibody Monitoring in Individuals at Risk of Occupational Exposure. *Vaccines*. 2021 Apr;9(4):309.
58. **Jonker EF, Visser LG.** Single visit rabies pre-exposure priming induces a robust anamnestic antibody response after simulated post-exposure vaccination: results of a dose-finding study. *Journal of travel medicine*. 2017 Sep 1;24(5).
59. **Fooks AR, Koraka P, de Swart RL, Rupprecht CE, Osterhaus AD.** Development of a multivalent paediatric human vaccine for rabies virus in combination with Measles-Mumps-Rubella (MMR). *Vaccine*. 2014 Apr 11;32(18):2020-1.
60. **Madhusudana SN** et al. Feasibility of reducing rabies immunoglobulin dosage for passive immunization against rabies: Results of in vitro and in vivo studies. *Hum Vaccin Immunother*. 2013; 9(9): 1914–1917.
61. **Saesow N** et al. Diffusion and fate of intramuscularly injected human rabies immune globulin. *Acta Trop*. 2000 ;76: 289–292.
62. **Wilde H** et al. Worldwide rabies deaths prevention – A focus on the current inadequacies in postexposure prophylaxis of animal bite victims. *Vaccine*. 2015;17:1–3.
63. **Bharti OK** et al. Injecting rabies immunoglobulin (RIG) into wounds only: A significant saving of lives and costly RIG. *Hum Vaccin Immunother*. 2017; 13(4):762–765.
64. **Bharti OK** et al. Local infiltration of rabies immunoglobulins without systemic intramuscular administration: An alternative cost-effective approach for passive immunization against rabies. *Hum Vaccin Immunother*. 2016; 12(3):837–842.
65. **WHO** Quality assurance of pharmaceuticals: a compendium of guidelines and related materials. Vol. 2, *Good manufacturing practices and inspection*. – 2nd ed, 2007.
66. **Warrell M.** Current rabies vaccines and prophylaxis schedules: Preventing rabies before and after exposure. *Travel Med Infect Dis*. 2012; 10:1–15.
67. **WHO.** Evidence to recommendation Table 3: prioritization of RIG. 2018. Available from http://www.who.int/immunization/policy/position_papers/rabies_prioritization_rig.pdf, Accessed on 28 May 2021.
68. **Sparrow E, Torvaldsen S, Newall AT, Wood JG, Sheikh M, Kieny MP,** et al. Recent advances in the development of monoclonal antibodies for rabies post exposure prophylaxis: a review of the current status of the clinical development pipeline. *Vaccine*. 2019 Oct 3;37:A132-9.
69. **WHO.** Report of the sixth WHO consultation on monoclonal antibodies in rabies diagnosis and research, Part II; 2-3 April 1990. Philadelphia, USA: The Wistar Institute. p. 6–9. Available from https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/61437/WHO_Rab.Res.90.34.pdf, Assessed on 28 May 2021.
70. **Serum Institute of India PVT. LTD.** Rabishield rabies human monoclonal antibody. Available from https://www.seruminstitute.com/product_ind_rabishield.php, Accessed on 29 May 2021.
71. **Gogtay NJ, Munshi R, Ashwathnarayan DH, Mahendra BJ, Kshirsagar V, Gunale B,** et al. Comparison of a novel human rabies monoclonal antibody to human rabies immunoglobulin for post-exposure prophylaxis: a phase 2/3 randomized, single blind, non-inferiority, controlled study. *Clin Infect Dis* 2017.
72. **Gogtay N, Thatte U, Kshirsagar N, Leav B, Molrine D, Cheslock P,** et al. Safety and pharmacokinetics of a human monoclonal antibody to rabies virus: a randomized, dose-escalation phase 1 study in adults. *Vaccine* 2012;30:7315–20.
73. **De Benedictis P, Minola A, Rota Nodari E, Aiello R, Zecchin B, Salomoni A,** et al. Development of broad-spectrum human monoclonal antibodies for rabies post-exposure prophylaxis. *EMBO Mol Med* 2016;8:407–21.
74. **Marissen WE, Kramer RA, Rice A, Weldon WC, Niezgodna M, Faber M,** et al. Novel rabies virus-neutralizing epitope recognized by human monoclonal antibody: fine mapping and escape mutant analysis. *J Virol* 2005;79:4672–8.
75. **Kuzimina NA, Kuzmin IV, Ellison JA, Rupprecht CE.** Conservation of binding epitopes for monoclonal antibodies on the rabies virus glycoprotein. *J Antiviral Antiretrovirals* 2013;5:37–43.
76. **WHO.** Background paper: proposed revision of the policy on rabies vaccines and rabies immunoglobulins. Prepared by the SAGE working group on rabies vaccines and immunoglobulins and the World Health Organization (WHO) Secretariat September 22, 2017. Available from https://www.who.int/immunization/sage/meetings/2017/october/1_Background_paper_WG_RABIES_final.pdf, Accessed on 29 May 2021.
77. **Kansagra K, Parmar D, Mendiratta SK, Patel J, Joshi S, Sharma N,** et al. A Phase 3, Randomised, Open-Label, Non-inferiority Trial Evaluating Anti-Rabies Monoclonal Antibody Cocktail (Twinrab™) Against Human Rabies Immunoglobulin (HRIG). *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2019 Oct 2.

78. **Synermore website** – Pipeline – SYN023. Available from <https://www.synermore.com/pipeline?t=SYN023>, Accessed on 29 May 2021.
79. **Twinrab**. Package Insert. Available from: <https://twinrab.com/>, Accessed on 29 May 2021
80. **Kasi SG, Shivananda S, Marathe S, Chatterjee K, Agarwalla S, Dhir SK**, et al. Indian Academy of Pediatrics (IAP) Advisory Committee on Vaccines and Immunization Practices (ACVIP): Recommended Immunization Schedule (2020–21) and Update on Immunization for Children Aged 0 Through 18 Years. *Indian Pediatrics*. 2021 Jan;58(1):44-53.
81. **WHO Modelling Rabies Consortium**: Modelling the potential impact of improved provision of rabies post-exposure prophylaxis in Gavi-eligible countries.
82. **Ponsich A** et al. A prospective study on the incidence of dog bites and management in a rural Cambodian, rabies-endemic setting. *Acta Trop*. 2016;160:62–67.
83. **Terrestrial Animal Health Code** Chapter 7.7, 6th Edition. World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE), France, 2017. Available from https://rr-africa.oie.int/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/en_csat-vol1-2017.pdf, Accessed on 30 May 2021.
84. **Coleman PG**. Immunization coverage required to prevent outbreaks of dog rabies. *Vaccine*. 1996; 14(3): 185–186.
85. **Mindekem R** et al. Cost Description and Comparative Cost Efficiency of Post-Exposure Prophylaxis and Canine Mass Vaccination against Rabies in N'Djamena, Chad. *Front Vet Sci*. 2017;4:38.
86. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (**FAO**), World Organisation for Animal Health (**OIE**), Global Alliance for Rabies Control (**GARC**) and country partners.
87. **WHO**. Zero by 30 our catalytic response. 2018. Available from <https://www.who.int/initiatives/united-against-rabies>, Accessed on 30 May 2021.
88. **United Nations**: Sustainable Development Goals. Available from <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>, Accessed on 30 May 2021.
89. **Wallace RM, Cliquet F, Fehlner-Gardiner C, Fooks AR, Sabeta CT, Setién AA**, et al. Role of Oral Rabies Vaccines in the Elimination of Dog-Mediated Human Rabies Deaths. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*. 2020 Dec;26(12).